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DEVELOPMENT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article examines the transformation of information and communication technologies and their impact on economic growth in the context of digitalization. The development of the digital economy signifies the country's transition to a new stage of development, creating broad opportunities for democratic progress and the improvement of national and economic governance systems. In the current environment, there is a growing need to reconsider digital governance tools and technologies by taking into account modern digitalization trends and ensuring a reasonable balance between the principles of open governance and economic security.

Key words: information and communication technologies, digital economy, innovation, internet, competitiveness, information society, patterns, trends, development, marketing, forecasting, activity, government.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasida axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari rivojlanishining transformatsiyasi va uning raqamlashtirish sharoitida iqtisodiy o'sishga ta'siri tahlil qilinadi. Raqamli iqtisodiyotning rivojlanishi mamlakatning yangi rivojlanish bosqichiga kirishini anglatib, jamiyatning demokratik rivojlanishi hamda milliy va iqtisodiy boshqaruv tizimini takomillashtirish uchun keng imkoniyatlar yaratadi. Bugungi sharoitda raqamli boshqaruv vositalari va texnologiyalarini zamonaviy raqamlashtirish tendensiyalarini hisobga olgan holda qayta ko'rib chiqish, ochiq boshqaruv talablari va iqtisodiy xavfsizlik o'rtasida oqilona muvozanatni ta'minlash muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari, raqamli iqtisodiyot, innovatsiya, internet, raqobatbardoshlik, axborot jamiyati, qonuniyatlar, tendensiyalar, rivojlanish, marketing, prognozlash, faoliyat, davlat.

Аннотация. В статье рассмотрены вопросы трансформации развития информационно-коммуникационных технологий и их влияния на экономический рост в условиях цифровизации. Развитие цифровой экономики означает вступление страны в новую фазу развития и открывает широкие возможности для демократического развития общества, а также совершенствования системы государственного и экономического управления. В современных условиях возрастает необходимость пересмотра инструментов и технологий цифрового управления с учетом актуальных тенденций цифровизации и обеспечения рационального баланса между требованиями открытости управления и экономической безопасностью.

Ключевые слова: информационно-коммуникационные технологии, цифровая экономика, инновации, интернет, конкурентоспособность, информационное общество, закономерности, тенденции, развитие, маркетинг, прогнозирование, активность, государство.

INTRODUCTION

The development of the information and communications technology (ICT) sector enhances the competitiveness of a national economy in the global market and contributes to the country's transition to a new stage of development characterized by intensive structural shifts in favor of a high-tech information sector. Global experience demonstrates that economic competitiveness is closely linked to the level of ICT development. According to the World Economic Forum, a strong correlation exists between a country's economic competitiveness index and its ICT development index, while the information technology industry remains one of the most dynamically growing sectors worldwide. The expansion of ICT in the public sector, the development of e-services, and increased investment in digital infrastructure stimulate the broader use of information technologies in the private and corporate sectors. Large-scale implementation of the open data concept creates a foundation for the emergence of new information services and improves the efficiency, transparency, and accessibility of information systems for citizens and businesses. In recent years, various components of e-government have been actively developed in Uzbekistan, and further computerization of key economic sectors, along with government-led digital transformation projects, has accelerated the creation of

new enterprises and the modernization of existing ones, potentially leading to the emergence of breakthrough, industry-specific technological solutions.

In this context, innovative marketing plays an increasingly important role as an integrated system combining strategy, business philosophy, and management functions. In industrialized economies, the marketing concept has become a central element of enterprise development. The primary objective of strategic innovative marketing is to design an effective strategy for introducing innovations into the market, which requires comprehensive market analysis, segmentation, demand formation, and modeling of consumer behavior. Strategic marketing is therefore closely linked to product positioning and demand forecasting based on consumer perceptions of innovation [1]. Effective strategic marketing research involves determining which products, of what quality, and for which target consumers an innovation project should be developed. This process requires continuous interaction between marketing departments, sociological research units, and consumers through surveys, interviews, and representative sampling. At the same time, analyzing operational problems within an organization is critical for stabilizing its position, as crises may arise from both internal and external environmental factors. As external environmental entropy increases, the formulation of anti-crisis measures becomes more complex, and marketing departments must identify related functional units, such as logistics or IT, whose instability may affect market performance and customer relations.

This integrated approach enables early identification of risk vectors and improves preparedness for adverse scenarios. When developing marketing plans and budgets, past expenditures are evaluated against achieved sales outcomes, and future objectives are set based on previous performance and anticipated market changes. Under conditions of moderate environmental instability, forecasts may rely on extrapolation of historical trends; however, as uncertainty and chaos intensify, forecasting increasingly depends on expert assessments and scenario analysis, including consideration of new external factors that may influence business activity.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The theoretical foundations and patterns of development of the information society were studied. The following foreign and domestic authors, who dedicated their scientific works to this topic, examined its impact on economic growth and increased competitiveness of the national economy. These authors include P.F. Drucker, B. Twiss, J. Schumpeter, I. Perlaki, N. Monchev, V.D. Hartman, R. Fostr, K. Oppenländer, B. Santo, A.M. Kadyrov, B.B. Abdullaev, and others.

Wanda J. Orlikowski and C. Suzanne Iacono focused on the theoretical aspects of the digital economy, with particular attention paid to the importance of databases [2].

R. Solow outlines the trends in economic growth over the past 50 years and development over the next 10 years, in which research on the replacement of the digital economy is detailed in the author's scientific works [3].

Tsoi M.P. He believes the digital economy is entering not only everyday life but also all spheres of production and services. In large companies and enterprises, particularly in Uzbekistan, business is structured according to internal rules known as corporate governance.[4]

G.Sh. Khankeldieva demonstrated the importance of innovation processes in promoting innovation as a key driver of economic growth and the development of a number of strategic documents at the state level aimed at ensuring the transition of the domestic economy to an innovative development path [5].

M.P. Eshov, in his research, studied the development of the digital economy and also demonstrated the importance of creating a national system of digital economic security. The concept of a "National System of Digital Economic Security" represents a complex political, legal, organizational, technical, and sociocultural system consisting of a set of objects and entities that guarantee national digital economic security [6]. F.O. Bazarov stated, "The development of the information and communications technology (ICT) sector can enhance the economy's competitiveness in the global market and will also contribute to the country's advancement to a new level of development, characterized by intensive structural shifts in favor of a high-tech information sector." [7]

K.U. Turaboeva believes that the development of the digital economy in Uzbekistan is a priority area of state economic policy. The digital economy, operating on information technology platforms, is developing at an intensive rate, necessitating the creation of new models and technologies for such platforms.[8]

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This article employs a set of complementary research methods and techniques, including theoretical methods of cognition and a systems approach to achieve a comprehensive theoretical understanding of the digital economy. Methods of analysis and synthesis are applied to generalize research findings, while comparison and measurement are used to identify structural and dynamic differences. In addition, the inductive method

is utilized to generalize the outcomes of digital economy implementation. The study is based on comparative and analytical approaches aimed at an in-depth examination of the research problem and the identification of strategic directions for its resolution. The objects of the study are the key indicators of the digital economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The experience of developed countries shows that the development of new information and telecommunications technologies not only directly impacts the competitiveness of national economies but also plays a decisive role in the formation of effective research and education sectors. In recent years, many countries and international organizations have prioritized the implementation of concepts and programs for the transition to an information society. Similar concepts have been developed and are being implemented in the United States, Great Britain, Canada, Finland, France, Japan, Italy, India, and elsewhere. These documents take diverse forms, but share a common goal: to become leaders in the global information community. The transition to an information society brings with it fundamentally new, interconnected changes in the socioeconomic structure of society, which in turn are driven by the development and objective impact of new, more sophisticated and more productive means of production. The primary objective is to harness the potential of the republic's research and development sector to effectively implement national technological development priorities, while simultaneously transforming the information and communications sector into a productive branch of the "knowledge economy." Prospective research requires examining the following key aspects of this problem:

- conceptual approaches to the strategy for integrating the republic's information and communications sector into the global market;
- areas for improving the institutional framework to create favorable conditions for the development of an innovative information-based economy;
- social factors (youth participation, education, etc.) in the development of the information and communications sector and opportunities for their effective use;
- strategies for creating incentives for the transition to an information society model in the context of post-crisis development of the national economy.

Thus, the results obtained in this research will expand scientific and methodological approaches to the formation of an information society, the creation of new conditions and sources for increasing the country's competitiveness, and mechanisms for their adaptation to the challenges of globalization of the world economic system. Modern Uzbekistan is part of the global economic community, and therefore ongoing integration processes in the international market require industrial organizations to enter the information society not only at the national level but also at the global level [9]. In terms of communications equipment production, China, India, and Asia-Pacific countries hold the largest positions in the ICT sector. Sales range from 13% to 20% of total revenue. China already controls 11% of the market, just 1% behind Japan. In terms of network equipment, Gartner analysts say cloud and mobile solutions will be the main drivers for enterprises. Demand for Ethernet switches in data centers will be driven by virtualization and cloud solutions, while the proliferation of mobile access points continues to drive significant demand for wireless LAN equipment. Software such as CRM, DBMS, data integration, and data quality tools will be in demand. With the development and implementation of modern information and communications technologies and the creation of infrastructure, there is a need to quickly engage the population with new technologies. In summary, the development strategy of the National Information and Communications System of the Republic of Uzbekistan, implemented in all areas of information and communications technology development, is showing positive trends. Particular attention is being paid to developing the domestic software market. As part of measures to further strengthen incentives for domestic software developers, a National Registry of Software Developers has been created, which already includes 69 domestic companies. The domestic software developer directory, software.uz, contains information on 1,600 domestic software products [3].

One of the industry's challenges is a shortage of qualified personnel. However, there is a shortage of qualified programmers. At most universities, programming is an applied discipline, as universities train programmers for specific industries such as transportation, mechanical engineering, and so on. However, information on specialization is often excessive, and programming skills training is insufficient.

Increased attention must be paid to increasing the number of graduates in IT-related fields, which form the initial pool of specialists for employment in the industry. According to the experience of a number of companies, IT graduates have virtually no advantage over physics, mathematics, or engineering graduates when applying for positions in software development and architecture. In addressing the systemic problem of developing the information and communications sector of the national economy over the long term, it is important to follow two key principles:

- Concentration of resources on funding research and development in key ICT areas, which means: expanded reproduction of fundamental and applied knowledge; and improved quality of human capital, potentially one of Uzbekistan's key competitive advantages in this area;
- Creation of an information infrastructure that enables the transformation of knowledge into marketable products through public-private partnerships.

It is assumed that some scientific research and the creation of an information infrastructure should be carried out with government participation, while market commercialization should be carried out primarily by businesses themselves.

At the same time, it is necessary to take into account development trends in the global information and communication technology market, where ICT production is shifting from developed to developing countries [10]. These trends have become catalysts for the development of ICT production, where their significant investment is directed. This is explained by the fact that these products are produced, with no less quality, but at lower costs in most developing countries, which increases the competitiveness of their products in the global market. Overall, the ICT market has become one of the most dynamic and capacious sectors of the global economy, which in turn has led to increased international competition in this area and prompted many countries to increase spending on research and development, innovation and product promotion to ensure leadership in the global ICT industry.

An analysis of the characteristics of demand formation in the global digital technology market, based on the specific requirements for the specific characteristics of a given product, allows us to identify three main consumer groups that drive global demand for information technology (Table 1).

One of the main reasons for the broad definition of ICT services is the convergence of technologies. In particular, it is currently extremely difficult to distinguish between computer, commercial, telecommunications, and software services. In our opinion, a broad definition of ICT services is preferable, as it allows for a more accurate assessment of the contribution and role of these services in global services trade. Therefore, when examining trade in ICT services, we adopt this broad definition.

Table 1. Key consumer groups driving global demand for digital technologies [15]

No	Name	Content
1	Private and public enterprises engaged in industrial production and services	The work notes that in the context of increasing competition in virtually all sectors of the global economy, companies, striving to improve management efficiency, ensure stable demand for various integrated management systems (Enterprise Resource Planning Systems - ERP Systems, Customer Relationship Management Systems - CRM Systems, Product Service Management Systems - PSM Systems), the sales revenues of which are growing annually worldwide;
2	Research organizations and universities	They form the main demand for application software for solving scientific research problems, automating the activities of financial and administrative departments, national libraries, for infrastructure software for personal computers and for the services of computing centers for processing large volumes of information.
3	Households	They primarily demand software for personal computers for processing text, audio, video and graphic information.

The selection of tools should be based on the principles of marketing for unstable organizations (unstable state), namely:

- value for the consumer, comprehensiveness and systematicity, urgency of response, adequacy of response to the degree of real threat to the organization's financial and market position, multi-variance and creativity, flexibility and adaptability, and the principle of prospectivity.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Thus, the following marketing tools were selected:

- conducting joint industry research with other market participants;
- implementing a new CRM system based on Big Data;
- developing transformative tariffs (moving away from the mass market toward product customization);
- creating mobile apps that provide unique services to subscribers, including through advertising projects;
- using proprietary and digital tools to minimize the time between initial contact with the brand and purchase (using QR codes, the ability to purchase new devices, change tariffs directly from a mobile phone, IPTV set-top box);

- participating in promotions held by retailers;
- integrating the work of agencies providing creative development and media planning services;
- analyzing the product line to increase promotion of key products (profit drivers) and reduce the promotion of products that are in the “mature” stage – mobile communication plans without mobile internet;
- Reducing the cost per thousand contacts (CPT) by refining target audiences based on more precise digital targeting;
- Actively managing social media marketing (SMM), including for technical support;
- Viral marketing (offline and online: creating branded internet portals, using non-standard media, etc.);
- Buzz marketing (conducting teaser campaigns, integrating services and products into everyday life using fictitious “happy customers” – using “life placement”);
- Actively using B2B exhibitions and hosting in-house business events;
- Managing a subscriber base by loyalty level. At the tenth stage, performance indicators and the planned quantitative assessment for each marketing tool are determined to evaluate effectiveness. If the organization does not have the capacity to calculate the necessary indicators, then it is necessary to abandon the implementation of a tool that cannot be evaluated.

Therefore, identifying the prerequisites and characteristics of various foreign models for entering global information societies is necessary for developing ICT development programs and institutional environments for Uzbekistan's entry into global information societies, identifying potential partners and competitors. In our view, the focus should be on those ICT industry segments in which domestic companies have competitive advantages in the domestic market, as well as segments of the global ICT market that have potential for promising growth.

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